

Shannon's Entropy and Determinism? Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that Shannon's entropy, $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$, in the case of a $p(i)$ which follows a uniform distribution becomes: $\ln(\text{number of attributes})$. We argued that this formula may be applied to a probabilistic (i.e. uncertain) situation of a toss of a die or coin, but could equally well be interpreted as simply the \ln of the number of attributes of an object, which has nothing necessarily to do with probability or uncertainty. In particular, one may argue that $p(i) = 1/B$, where B is the number of attributes, is simply a number with the property that $B/B=1$.

Here, we consider the case of $p(i)$ not being uniform. In such a case, $p(i)$ values may be interpreted as being due to uncertainty (probability) in a physical problem, i.e. a loaded die. We suggest, however, that there exists a purely deterministic physical scheme in which $p(i)$ and $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ has nothing to do with probability or uncertainty, but Shannon's entropy still exists as a mathematical formula. In particular, we consider the following example. We start with a certain amount of a substance, N , on Jan. 1 and argue that for the first 28 days of each month (for b months), one uses N such that after 28 days, amount remaining at the first of each month $\times p(i)^{28}$ is the new amount remaining. There is nothing probabilistic or uncertain about this. Then, the amount left after b days is:

$$\text{Amount left} = N \prod_{i=1, b} p(i)^{28} \quad ((1))$$

Taking \ln of both sides leads to Shannon's entropy arising as a measure for a purely deterministic scenario, we argue. One may argue that \ln is not needed, but it allows for $\ln(\text{amount type 1}) + \ln(\text{amount type 2}) = \ln(\text{product})$ which is \ln of the ways to arrange the different remaining amounts with each piece having its own identity/label. Again, this need not be probabilistic (although it could be) as there may be a recipe for the sequence of arrangements.

Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy may be obtained from:

$$\ln\left\{ \frac{N!}{\prod_i n(i)!} \right\} \quad ((2)) \quad \text{with the use of Stirling's approximation: } \ln(n(i)!) = n(i) \ln(n(i)) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } -\sum_i n(i) \ln(n(i)) + \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

In principle, ((2)) is the mathematical formula for a set of arrangements with $n(i)$ identical items for each i . It is possible to assign each arrangement (unique) to a possible outcome in a physical problem and in such a case one is dealing with a uniform probability distribution. The question is: Can one provide a deterministic interpretation for ((2)) as well? We argue that one

can. Each unique arrangement in ((2)) may be mapped to a fixed time. In such a case, one knows exactly when each arrangement appears in time and there is no uncertainty. ((2)) Thus, we argue that ((4)) is a math measure linked to arrangements, but does not necessarily have anything to do with probability. Of course, one may use it in probabilistic situations, such as the case of an ideal gas.

Result of Part 1

In Part 1, we focused on Shannon's entropy ((4)) for $p(i) = 1/B$, where B is the number of attributes of an object. $p(i)$ may then be associated with a uniform probability distribution, as in the case of a coin or die toss, but does not have to be. If one has a coin or die, one does not have to toss them and in such a case there is no probability, only a certain number of attributes. Thus, $\ln(B)$ may be interpreted as a non-probabilistic \ln of the number of attributes of an object such as a coin or die.

Nonuniform $p(i)$

Given a set of nonuniform $p(i)$ such that $\sum_i p(i) = 1$, and $0 \leq p(i) \leq 1$, one is trained to see these as probabilities, but we argue that they are simply a set of numbers with a particular constraint. One may certainly apply them to a probabilistic scenario which appears in nature, but they may also be applied to strictly deterministic scenarios.

In particular, we consider the following scenario. Imagine that one has an amount N of a certain quantity on Jan. 1st. Second, consider that there exists a $p(i)$ number of each month 1 to b such that $\sum p(i) = 1$. Next, consider that the amount of substance at the end of each month is:

$$p(i)^{28} \cdot \text{amount present at the first of the month} \quad ((5))$$

If one then writes: $N \prod_{i=1}^b p(i)^{28}$ and takes \ln of this result:

$$\ln(\text{amount remaining after } b \text{ months}) = \sum_i p(i)^{28} \ln(p(i)) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is $-28 \cdot$ Shannon's entropy, but this quantity arises for a completely deterministic scenario. There is no probability whatsoever, it seems. One may ask: Why is \ln of the amount remaining and not the amount itself the relevant quantity. We argue that if one has two different kinds of quantities, each with their own set of $p(i)$ s then:

$$\begin{aligned} & \ln(\text{amount remaining type 1}) + \ln(\text{amount remaining type 2}) \\ & = \ln(\text{product}) \quad ((7)) \end{aligned}$$

In other words, if one uses \ln and adds, then one gets \ln of the number of combinations of arrangements of the remaining amount of one type with the other in various ways. Again this

does not have to be probabilistic because one may have a deterministic reason for the various groupings. For example, at the end of b months, one may arrange the remaining items of type 1 with those of type 2 in a particular prescribed manner. The next month, one may choose a different prescribed grouping etc. In such a case, $\ln(\text{product})$ ((7)) has meaning, but is not in any way probabilistic.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that even though Shannon's entropy, $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$, may be applied to probabilistic scenarios in nature, it may also be used as a math description of purely deterministic scenarios as well. In part I, we focused on $p(i) = 1/B$ (a uniform distribution) or in the case of determinism, simply a 1 over the number of attributes of an object. Then $\ln(B)$ is the \ln of the number of attributes of say a coin or die which is not even tossed and so cannot be linked with probability. Here, we consider $p(i)$'s that are not uniform, but satisfy $\sum_i p(i) = 1$. Again, $p(i)$ may be said to represent a probability and be applied to a probabilistic situation, such as an ideal gas. We give an example in this note, however, which is strictly deterministic. We argue that given an amount N of a substance, one may have a rule which dictates that at the end of the month, one has: $p(i)$ power $(28^{*}p(i))$ of the amount one had at the first of the month. One may take a product over $i=1$ to b months and then take the \ln of this value, leading to Shannon's entropy appearing in a deterministic example. The \ln is useful in that if one wishes to add $\ln(\text{amount remaining})$ for different types of quantities, $\ln(\text{product})$ is linked with the number of arrangements of the remaining quantities, which each being numbered. This again does not need to be probabilistic because there may be a set of rules dictating the sequence in which various arrangements appear, hence removing probability.